

Use of 2-(3-Phenylthioureido)benzoic Acid in the Synthesis of Heterocycles and their Derivatives

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Similar to that reported earlier¹, present study reports the reaction of anthranilic acid with phenyl isothiocyanate in acetone to give 2-(3-phenylthioureido)benzoic acid as a key starting material for the preparation of some heterocyclic compounds expected to have biological activity. The reaction of 2-(3-phenylthioureido)benzoic acid with concentrated sulphuric acid yielded 3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4(1*H*,3*H*)-quinazolone (1) in excellent yield (Scheme 1).

The reaction of 1 with activated olefinic compounds such as β -(4-chlorobenzoyl)acrylic acid and β -(4-methylbenzoyl)acrylic acid under Michael reaction conditions in the presence of sodium methoxide afforded the corresponding Michael adducts (2a, b)².

Treatment of 2 with hydrazine derivatives such as hydrazine hydrate and phenylhydrazine in ethanol yielded the pyridazinone derivatives 3a, b and c respectively. The ethanolic solution of 3-phenyl-2-thioxo-4(1*H*,3*H*)-quinazolone with thiourea

gave the corresponding 3-phenyl-2-thioureido-4(1*H*,3*H*)-quinazolone (4). Compound 4 was fused with acetylacetone in the presence of sodium methoxide³ to afford the corresponding 4,6-dimethyl-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]pyrimidine-2-thione (5). Treatment of 4 with active methylene compounds⁴ such as ethyl acetoacetate and diethyl malonate in the presence of sodium methoxide, afforded the corresponding 4-methyl-6-oxo-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]-3(2*H*)-pyrimidinethione (6) and 6-hydroxy-2-thioxo-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]-4(3*H*)-pyrimidinone (7). Consequently, compound 4 was allowed to react with ethyl chloroacetate in pyridine to give 5-oxo-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]-2,4-dihydroimidazo-2-thione (8). The reaction of 4 with anisylidene ethyl cyanoacetate⁵⁻⁷ in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate yielded 5-cyano-4-anisyl-6-oxo-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]-3(2*H*)-pyrimidinethione (9).

Scheme 1

The ethanolic solution of **7** with hydrazine hydrate gave the corresponding 6-hydroxy-2-hydrazino-1-[3-phenyl-4*H*-quinazolone-2-yl]pyrimidin-(3*H*)-one (**10**).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillaries with a Thomas-Hoover Uni-Melt apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer using hexadeuteriodimethyl sulphoxide and tetramethyl silane as internal standard. Yields and physical data of various compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1–10*

Compd. no.	Colour	M.p.** °C	Yield %
1	Colourless	233 ^a	85
2a	Pale yellow	265 ^b	75
2b	Pale yellow	260 ^b	70
3a	Yellow	148 ^a	65
3b	Yellow	141 ^a	60
3c	Yellow	138 ^a	65
4	Colourless	260 ^a	70
5	Yellow	240 ^b	65
6	Yellow	233 ^b	55
7	Pale yellow	240	62
8	Colourless	229	53
9	Yellow	298	60
10	Colourless	160	68

3-Phenyl-2-thioxo-4(1*H*,3*H*)-quinazolone (1): 2-(3-Phenylthioureido)benzoic acid (0.015 mol) was swirled for a few minutes with concentrated H₂SO₄ (10 ml) to obtain a clear solution, and allowed to stand for 2 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-water and neutralised with solid or saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate, and the resulting solid was washed with water, air-dried and crystallised from ethanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 675 (C=O), 1 360 (C=S) and 3 220 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 7.1–8.1 (9H, m, ArH) and 11.4 (1H, s, NH).

Formation of 2a, b: A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and the active olefinic compound, namely, β -(4-chlorobenzoyl)acrylic acid and β -(4-methylbenzoyl)acrylic acid (0.01 mol) in sodium methoxide (50 ml) (0.005 g-atom sodium/25 ml methanol) was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and poured into dilute HCl (1%). The resulting solid was washed with water, air-dried and crystallised from a proper solvent: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 715–1 675 (C=O), 1 625 (C=N), 1 605 (C=O) and 3 450–2 850 cm⁻¹ (OH); **2a** δ (CF₃COOD) 2.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 4.1–4.3 (1H, t, CH), 6.8–8.2 (13H, m, ArH) and 10.5 (1H, s, OH).

Formation of 3a–c: A mixture of equimolecular quantities (0.01 mol) of **2** and hydrazine hydrate or phenylhydrazine in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled, poured into dilute HCl (1%) and the resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 685 cm⁻¹

(pyridazinone C=O) and absence of characteristic bands of C=O (acid and ketonic) and OH of acid.

Formation of 4: A mixture of equimolecular quantities (0.01 mol) of **1** and thiourea in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 675 (C=O), 1 355 (C=S), 3 405–3 285 and 3 210 cm⁻¹ (NH₂ and NH).

Formation of 5: A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol), acetylacetone (0.01 mol) and sodium methoxide (0.03 mol) was fused in an oil-bath at 170° for 2–3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed with dilute HCl and recrystallised from methanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 680 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N), 1 615 cm⁻¹ (C=C) and absences of bands of NH and NH₂; δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.1–2.4 (6H, br s, 2×CH₃) and 6.8–8.1 (10H, m, ArH and olefinic-H).

Formation of 6 and 7: A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol) and active methylene compound, namely, ethyl acetoacetate and diethyl malonate (0.01 mol) in sodium methoxide solution (50 ml) (0.005 g-atom sodium/25 ml absolute methanol) was heated for 6 h, then cooled and poured into dilute HCl (1%). The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent to give **6** and **7**: $\nu_{\max}$ 3 410–2 850 (OH), 1 695–1 675 (NH), 1 360 (C=O) and 1 180 cm⁻¹ (C=S); **6** δ (CF₃COOD) 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.7–8.0 (10H, m, ArH and olefinic-H) and 10.9 (1H, s, NH).

Formation of 8: A solution of **4** (0.01 mol) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol) in pyridine (30 ml) was refluxed for 15 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-cold solution of HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 1 720, 1 675 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N), 1 610 (C=C), 1 350 (C=S) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.3 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.9–8.0 (9H, m, ArH) and 9.9 (~0.6H, brs, NH–C=S).

Formation of 9: A mixture of **4** (0.01 mol), anisylidene ethyl cyanoacetate (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.03 mol) in ethanol (75 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into ice-cold dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from acetic acid: $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200 (NH), 2 140 (C=N), 1 680–1 660 (C=O), 1 350 and 1 180 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (CF₃COOD) 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.9–8.1 (13H, m, ArH) and 10.8 (1H, s, NH).

Formation of 10: A mixture of **7** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid obtained after cooling was dried and recrystallised from ethanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 3 450–2 850 (OH), 3 380 (NH), 3 200 (NH₂), 1 675–1 660 (C=O), 1 630 (C=N) and 1 605 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

References

1. E. P. PAFUDOPOULOS and C. D. TORRES, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1982, **19**, 269.

2. R. M. SALEH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 313.
3. W. WENDELIN, K. SCHERMANZ, K. SCHWEIGEN and A. FUCHSGRUBER, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1983, **114**, 1371.
4. M. BOTTA, M. COVATIERI, D. CECL, F. DE ANGELOSE, C. FINIZIA and R. NICOLETTI, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 3313.
5. N. TAKHHIKI and OMOTE, *J. Chem Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1978, 2523.
6. H. ENGLER and ISTVAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 547
7. A. L. GRIGORGAN and A. M. KALDRIKYAN, *Arm Khim Zh.*, 1987, **40**, 433.